

INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT OF ONION THRIPS (*Thrips tabaci* L.) AND ITS EFFECT ON ONION GROWTH AND YIELD (*Allium cepa* L.) UNDER IRRIGATION CONDITIONS IN GUBALAFTO DISTRICT, NORTH EASTERN ETHIOPIA

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ABSTRACT. Onion thrips is an insect pest that limits onion production and results in 26–57% output losses. Hence, a field experiment was carried out in the Gubalafto District of Ethiopia to create environmentally friendly management using intercropping vegetable and onion varieties. Three onion cultivars were used in the main plot treatment: Bombay red, Adama red, and Nafis. In the subplot treatments, tomatoes, carrots, and lettuce were intercropped with onions. Three replications of the study were carried out utilizing a split plot arrangement and a randomized complete block design. Ten randomly selected pre-tagged onion plants were used to gather data on the number of banded onion thrips and processed using SAS. The results demonstrated a reduction in onion thrips per plant when onion types were intercropped with vegetable treatments. The intercropping of Bombay red with tomato and Nafis with carrot decreased the population of onion thrips by 54.61% and 71.14%, respectively. Similarly, there was a significant decrease in the degree of thrips damage by 28.03% when Nafis was intercropped with carrots, with the maximum yield of onions (40.13 t/ha) achieved and the lowest (24.56 t/ha) from Adama red cropping alone. Carrots and Nafis intercropping had the highest gross income. The plot treated with Adama red had the lowest gross income. Intercropping onions with other vegetables, like carrots, was found to be effective in reducing the quantity of onion thrips and their damage to onions. As such, it can be a crucial part of the integrated management of onion thrips.

Keywords: cultural practices, onion varieties, thrips mortality, vegetable intercropping, yield

INTRODUCTION

The onion, *Allium cepa* L., is a biennial vegetable crop that is heavily farmed and has a monocotyledonous habit. The health benefits of onions have contributed to the gradual increase in the world's onion intake [1]. Grown at various latitudes, it is a major vegetable crop in Ethiopia and is used as a spice in most Ethiopian recipes.

In Ethiopia, onion has a large potential to produce annually for both domestic use and export. The total area under onion production was approximately 38,952.58 ha; of those, 3,460,480.88 tons were produced in 2020/2021, yielding an average output of 8.88 tons per hectare [2]. This indicates that Ethiopian onion production (8.8 t ha⁻¹) is significantly lower than the global average (18.8 t ha⁻¹) [3].

Onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* L.) are little, thin insects that are easily observed through a hand lens. When grown, onion thrips measure around 1.3 mm in length. The most unique feature of thrips is their two pairs of wings, each of which has a long hairy fringe. Adults are

light brown to pale yellow in colour. The immature stages are lighter in colour and lack wings, but they have the same body shape as the adult stages. In Ethiopia's onion-growing regions, it is a significant pest problem [4].

Many problems, such as insect pests, diseases, and insufficient pre- and post-harvest methods, contribute to Ethiopia's low yields and poor-quality shallot production [5]. The most common and dangerous insect pest of shallot is onion thrips, one of the several insect pests of allium crops. Both adults and larvae damage the plants by draining the sap from the leaves, which results in a lack of chlorophyll and a patchy silver appearance on the leaves. They also impair photosynthesis [6]. This major insect pest in Ethiopia can cause havoc on onion farms, especially during dry seasons, by rasping leaves and other onion crop tissues and releasing nutrients. It also lowers the quality and quantity of onions produced [7]. Due to onion thrips, yield losses of 26 to 57% for onion bulbs were occurred in Ethiopia. Comparable studies conducted in Ethiopia's Upper Awash Agro Industry Enterprises revealed that onion thrips reduced crops by 10% to 85% [8]. According to Shiberu et al. [9], yield losses in Ethiopia's Toke Kutaye region ranged up to 36.44%.

Intercropping is a sustainable technique in which a plant species (the intercrop) is purposely grown to reduce harm from pests on a primary crop [10]. In underdeveloped nations, subsistence farmers have long employed intercropping as a method of crop production [11]. The technique increases land productivity while utilizing fewer pesticides [12]. Gachu et al. [13] reported that intercropping onion with spider plant and carrot reduced thrips population by up to 45.2% and 21.6%, respectively. Research has also been carried out by intercropping different plant species to compare yield reductions with decreases in onion thrips colonization rates [14]. Predators of thrips are likely to be attracted to a mixed cropping habitat, as evidenced by studies on minute pirate bugs [15].

Host plant resistance, an essential component of integrated pest management, can also offer an extended method of controlling onion thrips and lessen the requirement for pesticides, lessening the hazards to the environment and the evolution of insecticide resistance [16]. Onion cultivars with tight necks and lighter green foliage attract thrips more than those with broad neck growth and dark, smooth leaves [17]. Onion thrips were less drawn to onion cultivars with yellow-green, glossy to semi-glossy leaf surfaces and an open neck than to those with blue-green, waxy leaves and tight necks [18].

At some point throughout the growing season, growers currently use insecticides to control thrips. The majority of insecticides are ineffective because thrips constantly hide amid the inner leaves of onion plants, and the pupa is buried in the soil. According to Nault and Shelton [19], onion thrips are a highly abundant species with two generations. According to reports, onion thrips have grown resistant to the majority of pesticides used today [20]. The usage of pesticides has detrimental effects on the environment and human fitness due to the high chemical residues, and it also drives up production costs [21]. It's critical to employ resistant varieties in conjunction with cultural techniques to effectively manage thrips and other onion pests.

Since onion thrips are an essential component of integrated pest management strategies, managing onion thrips must entail a combination of cultural practices and the use of tolerant varieties that reduce onion thrips populations. Therefore, this study assessed the level of resistance to onion thrips exhibited by several shallot cultivars and intercropping techniques.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the Study Area

Under irrigation, the field experiment was conducted in the Gubalafto District in northeastern Ethiopia in 2020–2021. Geographically, it is situated at latitude and longitude coordinates of 11°52' 33' N and 39° 31' 59' E, respectively, in the lowlands of the Amhara Region. The particular study site is 1745 meters above sea level, although the district as a whole lies between 1379 and 3809 meters above sea level. The average monthly temperature falls between 15 °C and 31 °C at its lowest and maximum. The amount of rainfall varies from year to year, is seasonal, and is poorly distributed over the region. The district has 500 to 800 mm of yearly precipitation on average [22]. There are four types of soil: silt soil (7%), sandy soil (8%), clay loam brown (39%), and sandy clay (46%). The main crops, vegetables, and fruits grown under both irrigation and rainfall circumstances include sugarcane, onion, potato, tomatoes, lettuce, carrot, *tef*, maize, sorghum, chickpea, cabbage, banana, orange, lemon, green pepper, and coffee [23].

Experimental Materials, Treatments and Experimental Procedure

The field experiment included three different onion varieties: Bombay red, Adama red, and Nafis. The Melkasa Agriculture Research Center introduced and modified each variety. They became adapted to altitudes between 700 and 2000 meters above sea level. Three types of onions—Bombay red, Adama red, and Nafis—three intercropping vegetables—carrots (*Daucus carota* L.), tomatoes (*Lycopersicon esculentum* L.), and lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.)—as well as an untreated control comprise the treatments. Three replications and a randomized complete block design (RCBD) were used to set up the experiment. The experimental plot measured 3.8 x 1.5 m, or 5.7 m², and the blocks were spaced 0.5 and 1 m apart, respectively, from the plots. For solo onion varieties, the distances between the ridges, furrows, and plants were 40 cm, 20 cm, and 10 cm, respectively. In the experimental field, the spacing between each variety of onion was immediately sown by drilling in the corresponding rows for the intercropping of carrots. Onion types, tomatoes, carrots, and lettuce had row and plant spacing (inter- and intra-row) of 20 cm * 10 cm, 70 cm * 30 cm, 25 cm * 5 cm, and 40 cm * 30 cm, respectively [24]. In one plot, each solo onion variety was planted in 12 rows; in the intercropping, carrots were planted in nine rows, tomatoes in five rows, and lettuce in seven alternate rows. Onion types were planted on one side of the ridge, while intercropping species were planted on the other. Each intercropping vegetable type (lettuce, carrot, and tomato) had seed rates of 6, 5, 0.3, and 0.2 kg/ha, in that order. In accordance with the advice for vegetable crops [24], NPS and UREA were applied.

Management of the Experimental field and Plants

For each variety, 5 x 1 m seedbeds were planted at a rate of 6.0 kg/ha with 95% germination of Bombay red, Nafis, and Adama red [24]. Different onion cultivars were sown with 2 cm-separating seeds and 15 cm-separating rows. In a 5 x 1 m seed bed, 300 grams of tomatoes and 200 grams of lettuce were sown, respectively. Five kg of carrot seed per hectare was sown in the main field. While tomato and lettuce seedlings were only kept in the nursery for 30 days, onion seedlings were kept for 50 days. To produce robust and healthy seedlings of every vegetable, all nursery management techniques, including mulching, watering, fertilizer application, and weeding, were carried out in accordance with the recommendation.

Carefully removed from nursery beds, seedlings were transferred to the main experimental field once they reached three or four true leaves. To help with seedling uprooting, the nursery bed was watered the day before transplantation. To maintain the intended plant population per plot, gap filling was done a week after transplanting in order to place healthy, strong, and uniform seedlings. In the main field, carrots were directly sown in the designated rows. Following germination, crowded seedlings were thinned down so that plants remained 5 cm apart.

The seedlings were moved to the prepared and irrigated experimental field after the land was manually harrowed and ploughed with oxen to create a fine tilt in the soil. The field was ploughed and irrigated twice a week for the first four weeks. After that, fertilizer NPS was transplanted at a rate of 5.22 kg/ha, and urea was applied twice at a rate of 2.48 kg/ha. Thirty days after transplantation, the second half was administered. The first half was applied during transplanting. All agronomic procedures were followed as advised for the production of onions, including weeding, cultivation, and chemical treatment. As soon as the plants attained physiological maturity, harvesting was done.

Data Collection

At 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, and 105 days after transplanting, data was gathered to count the number of banded onion thrips from ten randomly selected pre-tagged onion plants throughout the plot. The process involved visually inspecting every leaf on the tagged onion plants to check for banded thrips. The number of onion thrips was recorded at 15-day intervals, starting from the second week after transplantation and continuing until physiological maturity. Although not every plant was harvested at once, lettuce was harvested 35 days before onions. It has been continuously harvested for two weeks. The tomatoes took roughly four weeks to harvest, starting 25 days before the onions and carrots. The weight of single bulbs (g), yield per plot (kg), and yield per hectare (tons) from each variety and intercropping plots were recorded.

Onion Thrips Parameters Collected

Ten randomly chosen plants from each treatment plot, including intercropped vegetables and different onion kinds, were used to gather the thrips population. Using a 10x hand lens magnifier, both nymphs and adults were counted by looking at the entire plant. When there was no wind, either early in the morning or late in the afternoon, onion thrips were not flying from plant to plant and could be counted. Without disturbing the nymphs, counting was done by delicately separating each leaf of the upright plant.

Number of Thrips Per Plant: was counted with the help of a hand lens on tagged plant leaves, and the mean number per plant was calculated [9]. The percent reduction in the number of thrips per plant was calculated using the formula of Dutta et al. [25] as Eqn. 1.

$$\text{Percent thrips population reduction over untreated control} = \frac{\text{Mean of control} - \text{Mean of treatment}}{\text{Mean of control}} \times 100$$

Eqn. 1

Infestation of onion thrips was determined by counting onion thrips from ten plants in each plot, starting a week after transplantation and continuing until physiological maturity. The

percentage of thrips was calculated as a ratio of infested to total sampled tagged 10 plants [25] as Eqn. 2.

$$\text{Infestation of thrips} = \frac{\text{Number of infested plants}}{\text{Total plant observed}} \times 100$$

Eqn. 2

Onion thrips damage severity silvery patches ordinarily due to thrips on ten tagged onion leaves were taken into consideration to assess thrips damage severity. The leaves of each randomly tagged standing plant were examined to assess the severity on a scale of 1-5 based on Smith et al. [26], where 1 = no damage, 2 = up to 25%, 3 = 26–50%, 4 = 51–75%, and 5 = >75% damage.

Growth and Bulb Yield Parameter of Onions

At physiological maturity, which occurs after 50–80% of the foliage has fallen over and the plant roots and crowns have been removed, each net plot's bulbs were weighed, classified into non-split or non-double bulbs, and segregated into marketable and unmarketable bulbs.

Plant height

Plant height was measured from ten randomly tagged plants from the soil surface to the plant's apex using a ruler at the time of harvest.

Leaf length

The lengths of leaves of ten randomly sampled tag onion plants were measured from the pseudo-stem to the tip of the most extended leaves at physiological maturity using a ruler, and the mean values were computed for further analysis.

Leaf number

The number of leaves per plant counted was taken from randomly selected 10 tagged plants from each of the treatment plots a week before harvesting. The total number of leaves of ten randomly labelled plants taken from the net plot area was counted at physiological maturity, and the average number of leaves per plant was taken for further analysis.

Bulb weight (g)

At harvest, the average bulb weight of ten randomly chosen bulbs was calculated and used for further analysis.

Bulb length (cm)

Ten randomly chosen bulbs per plot were measured with calipers from the bottom to the top, and the mean value was calculated for further analysis.

Bulb diameter (cm)

Using calipers, the diameters of ten randomly chosen bulbs in each plot were measured to determine the mean size of the bulb at harvest.

Total biomass (g)

This was determined by the summation of the shoot and bulb weights of the sample plants measured in kilograms using a scaled balance and expressed as a ton per hectare.

Marketable bulb yield (t/ha)

Bulb sizes ranging from 20 to 160 g were considered appropriate for marketing as long as they were uniform in color, and free of mechanical, disease, and insect pest damage. Each plot's net area was used to calculate the weight of these bulbs, which was then measured in kilograms using a scaled balance and expressed as tons per hectare.

Unmarketable bulb yield (t/ha)

Bulbs harvested that were physiologically disturbed, undersized and large (20 g and >160 g), misshaped, decaying, discolored, and infected were unmarketable. Using a scaled balance, the weight of these bulbs that were determined from the net plot area of each plot was measured in kilograms and expressed as tons per hectare.

Total bulb yield (t/ha)

By combining the yields of marketable and unmarketable bulbs, the total onion yield was calculated and expressed as tons per hectare.

Data Analysis

The data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the effect of the treatment using the PROC-GLM of SAS software version 9.1. Treatment means were delineated using the Fisher's least significant differences (LSD) test at a 5% or 1% level of significance based on Gomez and Gomez [27]. Additionally, a simple Pearson correlation analysis was performed to reveal the magnitudes and directions of the thrips population and bulb yield.

Economic Analysis

The economic analysis was done according to CIMMYT [28] to calculate the incomes and expenses of each treatment used in the experiment. To calculate the gross incomes, the marketable yields obtained from each treatment of onion were downscaled by 10%. The marginal rate of return was calculated as Eqn. 3.

$$\text{MRR}\% = \frac{\text{change NI}}{\text{change TVC}}$$

Eqn. 3

Where: NI = change in net come,
TVC= Change in total variable cost,
MRR= Marginal rate of return

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of intercropping on the number of onion thrips reduced

At the beginning of the sample periods, there were few onion thrips per plant; however, the thrips population progressed up until the onion reached physiological maturity. According to

the analysis of variance and the main factor and interaction impact of onion cultivars and vegetable intercropping, the number of onion thrips at 15, 45, 60, 75, 90, and 105 days after transplantation (DAT) varied significantly ($p < 0.001$). The Adama red onion cultivar had the most onion thrips per plant at 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, and 105 days following transplantation (Table 1). Tomato intercropping with Bombay red at 15 DAT has the highest thrips count as well. The onion variety Nafis had the fewest thrips at 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, and 90 DAT, while the tomato-Nafis intercropped had the fewest thrips at 15 DAT. Similar to this study, Mulu et al. [29] found that the highest mortality percentage with the lowest population of thrips per onion plant was shown in the Adama red variety than Bombay red onion variety. After transplanting, the thrips population varied statistically ($p < 0.05$) in every treatment from day 15 to day 105. Onion intercropped with vegetables, however, showed a lower thrips population than onion solo crops from the first monitoring periods onward (Table 2). This could be due to the different varieties of onions and the notable impact of intercropping onions with vegetables.

Table 1. Effect of onion varieties on the number of onion thrips

Onion varieties	Day 15	Day 30	Day 45	Day 60	Day 75	Day 90	Day 115
Adama red	4.27 ^a	9.00 ^a	18.30 ^a	34.89 ^a	44.63 ^a	68.56 ^a	86.37 ^a
Bombay red	3.44 ^b	7.22 ^b	13.83 ^b	22.70 ^b	32.11 ^b	36.88 ^b	51.50 ^b
Nafis	3.18 ^b	6.81 ^b	12.65 ^c	22.67 ^b	29.88 ^c	35.79 ^b	45.00 ^c
Mean	3.63	7.68	14.94	26.75	35.54	47.07	60.95
LSD ($P \leq 0.05$)	0.42	0.94	0.72	1.23	1.43	2.62	2.51
Significant level		**	***	***	***	***	***
CV (%)	5.08	5.41	2.12	2.04	1.77	2.45	1.84

*** and ** = significant at $P \leq 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001 probability levels

The intercropping of Nafis with carrot at 15, 30, 60, 75, 90, and 105 DAT, Bombay red with carrot at 45 and 105 DAT, and Bombay red with lettuce at 90 DAT resulted in the largest reduction in the thrips population. The intercropping of Bombay red with tomato at 15 DAT, Adama red with carrot at 30 DAT, Nafis with lettuce at 30, 45, 60, and 105 DAT, Adama red with lettuce at 75 DAT, and Bombay red with lettuce at 90 DAT yielded the lowest reduction in the thrips population (Table 3).

At 105 DAT, there were more thrips in all treatments. This might be because the lack of rain has created an ideal environment for onion thrips. In comparison to solo cropping, the intercropping of onion cultivars treated with vegetables resulted in a considerable reduction of onion thrips per plant. The intercrop crop species may be physically interfering with this. Along with giving predators food and cover, companion plants physically impede the movement of insect pests. It's likely that the presence of several plants makes it more difficult for an insect to identify a host plant by either physically hiding it or by releasing volatiles that make the insect confused.

When compared to onion varieties with intercropped treatments, solo cropping Adama red produced the highest amount of onion thrips per onion plant, suggesting the development of onion thrips in Adama red. Carrots and Nafis intercropping reduced insect pests (Table 2). Numerous investigators documented the impact of intercropping on the decline in the thrips population. According to Hossain et al. [30], intercropping tomatoes and carrots with onions dramatically decreased the number of thrips. According to Smith et al. [26], the onion's confusing visual and olfactory cues prevented the insects from spreading, which is why there were far fewer *Brevicoryne brassicae* on the intercropped plants. Intercropping onions with

carrots and tomatoes considerably reduced the population of thrips by up to 52.42% and 48.84%, respectively. Gebretsadkan et al. [31] report that intercropping the spider plant (*Chlorophytum comosum*) with carrot significantly reduced the thrips population in various onion cultivars. The spider plant achieved the largest reduction, up to 45.2% [32].

Because the non-host crop served as a physical barrier to the migration of insect pests, intercropping decreased the number of pest attacks. According to Smith and Liburd [33], an herbivore has to spend more time and energy looking for a plant that it can eat when it comes across one that it cannot. This shortens the insect's life span and energy needed to harm crops or lay eggs, and in certain cases, it even drives the insect away by discouraging it from staying in the region.

Table 2. Effect of intercropping on the mean number of thrips per plant

Onion varieties	Intercropping vegetable's	Day15	Day30	Day45	Day60	Day75	Day90	Day105
Bombay red	Carrot	2.28 ^{de}	4.33 ^e	6.28 ^e	12.10 ^{ef}	16.22 ^g	29.26 ^e	34.61 ⁱ
	Lettuce	2.53 ^{cd}	5.16 ^{cd}	5.52 ^e	10.36 ^f	21.33 ^f	32.27 ^{de}	42.11 ^g
	Tomato	2.90 ^{bc}	4.55 ^{de}	5.85 ^e	10.30 ^f	20.44 ^f	30.40 ^e	40.18 ^{gh}
Nafis	Bombay red	3.44 ^b	7.22 ^b	13.83 ^b	22.69 ^c	32.11 ^d	36.88 ^c	51.50 ^e
	Carrot	0.92 ^g	2.20 ^f	5.52 ^e	10.40 ^f	14.12 ^h	21.42 ^g	30.28 ^j
	Lettuce	1.78 ^{ef}	4.40 ^{de}	9.70 ^{cd}	19.16 ^d	21.63 ^f	31.03 ^e	39.69 ^h
	Tomato	1.68 ^f	4.20 ^e	7.20 ^{de}	12.86 ^e	16.06 ^g	25.23 ^f	35.56 ⁱ
Adama red	Nafis	3.18 ^b	6.81 ^b	12.68 ^{bc}	22.67 ^c	29.88 ^e	35.79 ^{cd}	45.00 ^f
	Carrot	2.58 ^{cd}	5.79 ^c	8.50 ^{de}	28.12 ^b	38.21 ^c	55.36 ^b	67.31 ^b
	Lettuce	2.30 ^{de}	4.71 ^{de}	12.68 ^{bc}	29.87 ^b	40.08 ^b	56.74 ^b	65.14 ^c
	Tomato	2.23 ^{def}	5.60 ^c	10.19 ^{cd}	28.49 ^b	39.37 ^{bc}	58.12 ^b	62.22 ^d
	Adama red	4.27 ^a	9.00 ^a	18.30 ^a	34.89 ^a	44.63 ^a	68.56 ^a	86.37 ^a
Mean		2.51	5.33	9.98	20.16	27.84	40.09	49.10
LSD (P≤0.05)		0.56	0.79	3.15	2.37	1.55	3.54	1.95
Significant level		**	***	*	***	***	**	***
CV (%)		13.24	8.76	19.26	6.97	3.31	2.09	2.30

*, ** and ***= significant at P≤0.05, 0.01 and 0.001 probability levels.

Table 3. Number of onion thrips reduction (%) over control

Onion varieties	Intercropping vegetables	Day 15	Day 30	Day 45	Day 60	Day 75	Day 90	Day105
Adama red	Carrot	39.53	35.73	53.54	19.39	14.39	19.25	22.07
	Tomato	47.81	37.84	44.29	18.33	11.79	15.23	27.95
	Lettuce	46.09	47.69	30.68	14.39	10.19	17.24	24.58
Bombay red	Adama red	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Carrot	33.88	39.95	54.98	46.67	49.48	20.67	32.78
	Tomato	15.78	37.00	57.70	54.61	36.35	17.56	21.97
	Lettuce	26.33	28.55	60.11	54.34	33.58	12.51	18.23
Nafis	Bombay red	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Carrot	71.14	67.65	56.47	54.11	52.74	40.15	32.72
	Tomato	47.01	38.37	43.19	43.27	46.26	29.54	20.98
	Lettuce	43.97	35.34	23.55	15.47	27.62	13.30	11.81
	Nafis	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Effects of Intercropping on thrips damage severity scale and Damage Severity Reduction

The degree of leaf damage score varied significantly between treatments. On the onion thrips damage severity scale at 15, 30, 45, 60, 90, and 105 DAT, an analysis of variance showed that the intercropping effect of onions and the main factor of onion types had a very highly significant ($p < 0.001$) difference. On the thrips damage severity scale at 15 and 75 DAT, however, the interaction effect of onion types and vegetable intercropping showed a significantly significant effect ($p < 0.01$). At 90 DAT, the extent of thrips damage was significant ($p < 0.001$). When compared to onion-solo harvests, the severity was often lower for onion types with vegetables intercropped (Table 4).

In onion varieties Adama red, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, and 105 DAT, as well as in vegetable intercropping Adama red with lettuce at 15, 30, 75, 90, and 105 DAT, Adama red with tomato at 15 and 105 DAT, and Bombay red with lettuce at 45 and 60 DAT, the highest damage severity scale of onion thrips per onion plant was recorded (Table 4). At 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, and 105 DAT, the onion variety Nafis had the lowest scale of onion thrips per onion plant. When intercropping Nafis with tomato at 15 and 75 DAT, Nafis with carrot at 30, 45, 60, 90, and 105 DAT, and Nafis with lettuce at 60 DAT, the severity of the damage from thrips was low during the first sampling (15 DAT), but gradually increased over time in the onion crop (Table 4).

When Nafis were intercropped with carrots until they reached physiological maturity, the degree of thrips damage was the smallest. On the other hand, the most severe thrips damage was observed when Adama red was cropped alone until physiological maturity. On the mean scale of the treated plots = 3.64 at 105 DAT, about 50% of the Adama red onion leaves were injured (Table 4). This can be because each plant has the greatest number of infestations (86.37 onion thrips). Damage from onion thrips feeding causes silvering of the leaf tissue and a decrease in photosynthesis, which reduces bulb size and reduces yield. By lowering the population of onion thrips, intercropping significantly lessened the severity of thrips damage. This can be due to physical, visual, and chemical interferences, in addition to the preservation of more natural enemies.

Table 4. *Effect of intercropping onion with other vegetables on thrips damage severity scale*

Onion varieties	Intercropping vegetables	Day 15	Day 30	Day 45	Day 60	Day 75	Day 90	Day 115
Adama red	Carrot	1.44 ^c	1.62 ^{cde}	1.64 ^f	1.86 ^d	2.04 ^{def}	2.84 ^c	3.12 ^c
	Tomato	1.43 ^c	1.60 ^{de}	1.72 ^{de}	1.86 ^d	2.06 ^{de}	2.85 ^c	3.26 ^b
	Lettuce	1.44 ^c	1.67 ^c	1.73 ^{de}	1.88 ^{de}	2.30 ^c	3.12 ^b	3.36 ^b
	Adama red	1.70 ^a	1.99 ^a	2.13 ^a	2.37 ^a	2.78 ^a	3.21 ^a	3.64 ^a
Bombay red	Carrot	1.21 ^{ef}	1.42 ^f	1.68 ^{ef}	1.85 ^d	1.93 ^{efg}	2.02 ^h	2.29 ^f
	Tomato	1.30 ^d	1.62 ^{cde}	1.79 ^{cd}	1.86 ^d	2.07 ^d	2.34 ^{fg}	2.50 ^e
	Lettuce	1.34 ^d	1.66 ^{cd}	1.82 ^c	1.93 ^{cd}	2.09 ^d	2.41 ^f	2.70 ^d
	Bombay red	1.53 ^b	1.82 ^b	1.90 ^b	2.15 ^b	2.60 ^b	2.61 ^d	3.09 ^c
Nafis	Carrot	1.21 ^e	1.21 ^h	1.33 ^h	1.58 ^f	1.92 ^{fg}	1.92 ⁱ	2.06 ^g
	Tomato	1.16 ^{fg}	1.32 ^g	1.51 ^g	1.78 ^e	1.88 ^g	2.04 ^h	2.26 ^f
	Lettuce	1.23 ^e	1.35 ^g	1.49 ^g	1.64 ^f	2.30 ^c	2.34 ^g	2.45 ^e
	Nafis	1.44 ^c	1.56 ^e	1.84 ^{bc}	2.04 ^{bc}	2.52 ^b	2.53 ^e	2.80 ^d
LSD		0.06	0.06	0.07	0.12	0.14	0.07	0.11
Sign. level		**	**	ns	ns	*	***	ns
CV		2.47	2.61	2.47	3.73	3.80	1.70	2.40

*, ** and ***= significant at $p \leq 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001 probability levels, ns=not significant at 5% probability levels

At 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, and 105 days after planting, the greatest reduction in the degree of thrips damage was observed when Nafis was intercropped with carrot. This was followed by Nafis with tomato and Bombay red with carrot at 75 and 90 days after planting. The intercropping of Adama red with lettuce at 90 and 105 DAT, Bombay red with tomato at 15 and 45 DAT, Bombay red with lettuce at 30, 45, and 60 DAT, and Nafis with lettuce at 15 and 75 DAT showed the lowest reduction in the degree of thrips damage. When compared to all other treatments, intercropping carrot with Nafis reduced the severity of thrips damage by 28.03% at 45 days after planting (Table 5).

The present study found a considerable influence of intercropping on thrips damage severity decrease, which is consistent with previous findings. According to Hossain et al. [30], intercropping onions with vegetables like tomatoes, carrots, and French beans greatly lessened the extent of thrips damage to the onions. Similar to this, AxARC [32] found that intercropping onions with french beans, carrots, and spider plants greatly decreased the severity of thrips damage to onions. When studying intercropping against onion thrips, Trdan et al. [10] found that onions interplanted with buckwheat (*Fagopyrum* spp.) and *Lacy phacelia* suffered the least amount of damage.

Table 5. Thrips damage severity reduction over control

Onion varieties	Intercropping vegetable's	Day 15	Day 30	Day 45	Day 60	Day 75	Day 90	Day 115
Adama red	Carrot	15.29	18.29	22.97	21.41	26.53	11.42	14.19
	Tomato	15.88	19.63	19.38	21.41	25.93	11.11	10.53
	Lettuce	15.10	15.94	18.91	20.56	17.05	2.80	7.78
Bombay red	Adama red	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Carrot	21.82	20.27	16.58	13.84	20.89	23.69	24.65
	Tomato	14.81	10.99	5.95	13.20	19.95	10.22	19.09
	Lettuce	12.20	8.79	4.55	10.25	19.18	7.66	12.51
Nafis	Bombay red	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Carrot	22.69	22.81	28.03	22.51	25.36	24.34	25.24
	Tomato	19.68	15.78	18.26	13.05	24.31	19.47	19.40
	Lettuce	14.81	13.86	18.99	19.90	9.25	7.76	12.62
	Nafis	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Effect of intercropping onion with other vegetables on onion thrips infestation

Analysis of variance showed that at 15, 30, and 45 days following treatment, the main and interaction effects of vegetable intercropping and onion types recorded a very highly significant ($p < 0.001$) effect on thrips infestation. On the other hand, there was no significant change ($p > 0.05$) in thrips infestation during the other sampling times of treatments at 60, 75, 90, and 105 DAT (Table 6).

At 15 DAT, the highest level of onion thrips infection was noted while intercropping Adama red with lettuce. Onion thrips, on the other hand, have contaminated the other treatment plots during the first sampling period, which was three weeks following the transplantation of vegetable intercropping and solo onion crops. The intercropping of Nafis with carrot at 15, 30, and 45 DAT resulted in the lowest infestation of onion thrips, or none at all (Table 6).

Rather than vegetable intercropping plots, solo onion patches had a high thrips infection. According to Gitonga et al. [34], in both the first and second trials, the unprotected plots had a much larger thrips infestation than the protected plots. According to Hossain et al. [30],

intercropping onions with tomatoes or carrots yielded a higher economic return when treating onion thrips infestations.

Table 6. *Effect of intercropping onion with other vegetables on onion thrips infestation*

Onion varieties	Intercropping vegetables	Day 15	Day 30	Day 45	Day 60	Day 75	Day 90	Day 115
Adama red	Carrot	86.67 ^{ab}	93.33 ^{ab}	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Lettuce	90.00 ^a	90.00 ^b	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Tomato	80.00 ^{bc}	93.33 ^{ab}	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
Bombay red	Adama red	93.33 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Carrot	86.67 ^{ab}	90.00 ^b	86.7 ^b	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Lettuce	76.67 ^c	90.00 ^b	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Tomato	76.67 ^c	86.67 ^b	96.67 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
Nafis	Bombay red	86.67 ^{ab}	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Carrot	0.00 ^d	30.00 ^c	86.67 ^b	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Lettuce	86.67 ^{ab}	90.00 ^b	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Tomato	76.67 ^c	90.00 ^b	96.7 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
	Nafis	90.00 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
LSD		9.67	7.17	3.81	0	0	0	0
Significant level		***	***	***	ns	ns	ns	Ns

*, ** and ***= significant at $P \leq 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001 probability levels; Ns=not significant at 5% probability level

Effect of intercropping onion with other vegetables on onion growth parameters

Plant height

According to the analysis of variance, the intercropping of vegetables with onion and solo onion types had a very highly significant effect ($p < 0.001$) on plant height. When Nafis was interplanted with carrots, the highest plant height was observed, followed by Nafis interplanted with tomatoes and lettuces. When intercropping Adama red with lettuce and solo cropping Adama red with Bombay red, the lowest plant height was observed (Table 7). This is consistent with the finding of Warwick et al. [35], who indicated that treating onions with intercropping reduced the insect population on onions and hence improved crop growth.

Number of leaves

The analysis of variance revealed that the number of leaves per plant of onion was very highly significant ($p < 0.001$). The maximum number of leaves per plant was recorded in Nafis with carrot, followed by the intercropping of Nafis with tomato, while the minimum number of leaves per plant was observed when intercropping Adama red with lettuce and solo cropping in Adama red (Table 7). According to research by Mulu et al. [29], the Bombay variety had the most leaves per plant, whereas the Adama variety had the fewest leaves per plant.

Leaf length

The leaf length of the solo and intercropping onion types was shown to be highly significant ($p < 0.001$) based on the analysis of variance. The intercropping of Nafis with lettuce and tomatoes yielded the longest leaves, followed by the intercropping of Nafis with carrots. On the other hand, when intercropping Adama red with lettuce and tomato or when growing Adama red alone, the lowest leaf length was observed (Table 7). The varying genetic compositions may

be the cause of the variations in leaf length. This outcome is consistent with that of Yemane et al. [36], who found that the Adama Red onion varieties showed higher leaf length than the Melkam and Bombay Red onion varieties.

Table 7. *Effect of intercropping onion with other vegetables on growth parameters of onion*

Onion varieties	Intercropping vegetables	Number of leaf	Plant height (cm)	Leaf length (cm)
Adama red	Carrot	9.56 ^{def}	46.51 ^f	34.36 ^d
	Tomato	8.79 ^f	43.30 ^g	32.87 ^e
	Lettuce	7.65 ^g	42.44 ^{gh}	32.09 ^e
	Adama red	7.30 ^g	41.27 ^h	31.72 ^e
Bombay red	Carrot	11.45 ^{bc}	52.63 ^c	36.82 ^c
	Tomato	10.56 ^{cd}	48.56 ^c	36.40 ^c
	Lettuce	10.30 ^{de}	50.01 ^{de}	36.91 ^c
	Bombay red	9.38 ^{ef}	41.51 ^h	35.02 ^d
Nafis	Carrot	13.32 ^a	59.37 ^a	43.47 ^a
	Tomato	11.73 ^b	57.14 ^b	41.25 ^b
	Lettuce	10.40 ^{cde}	55.8 ^b	40.03 ^b
	Nafis	10.51 ^{cd}	50.15 ^d	36.77 ^c
Mean		10.08	49.07	36.48
LSD (P<0.05)		1.02	1.50	1.32
Significant level		***	***	***
CV		5.97	1.81	2.13

***= significant at 0.001 probability levels

Effect of Intercropping on Yield and Yield Component Parameters of Onion

Analysis of variance revealed that the average bulb length of onion was very significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced by both the main and interaction effects of the onion yield component. The Nafis onion and carrot intercropped varieties have the longest bulb lengths on record. The onion cultivars Adama red and Bombay red interplanted with lettuce had the shortest bulb lengths (Table 8).

The results of the analysis of variance indicated that the intercropping effect of the diameter of the onion bulb and the main factor of onion had a very highly significant ($p < 0.001$) effect ($p < 0.001$) on onion yield. However, onion bulb diameter was not significantly affected by the interaction of vegetable intercropping with onions. The onion varieties of Nafis and Nafis interplanted with carrots and tomatoes had the largest bulb diameters. On Adama red, the lowest bulb diameter was observed (Table 8).

Analysis of variance revealed that the biomass weight, bulb weight, total bulb yield, unmarketable bulb yield, and marketable bulb yield of onions were highly significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced ($p < 0.001$) by both the main and interaction effects of the onion yield component. The highest bulb weight, biomass weight, total bulb yield, and marketable bulb yield were recorded when the Nafis variety was intercropped with carrot, followed by Nafis with tomato in total bulb yield and marketable bulb yield. The onion variety Nafis, followed by Bombay Red, recorded the highest bulb weight, biomass weight, total bulb yield, and marketable bulb yield (Table 8).

When tomatoes, lettuce, and carrots were interplanted with Adama red onions, the bulb biomass weight yield of onions was the lowest. Similarly, Bombay red intercropping with lettuce and tomato had the lowest bulb weight, marketable bulb yield, and total bulb yield of

onion. Adama red onion cultivars had the lowest bulb weight, biomass weight, total bulb yield, and marketable bulb yield measured. Compared to the untreated control solo onion types, onions intercropped with carrot, tomato, and lettuce produced the highest bulb length, bulb diameter, bulb weight, and biomass weight per plant (Table 8). This might be because there were fewer thrips, which reduced the crop. Similarly, the smallest measurements of bulb length, bulb diameter, bulb weight, and biomass weight were observed on onion varieties of Adama red. This might be due to the fact that the highest population of thrips occurred on Adama red, which severely damaged the crop.

The unmarketable bulb yield was significant ($p < 0.001$). Onion solo cropping with Adama red had the largest unmarketable bulb yield, while carrot intercropping with Nafis produced the lowest unmarketable yield (Table 8). In contrast to Trdan et al. [10], there was a decrease in onion yield when *Lacy phacelia* was interplanted with onions. According to Kabura et al. [37]), an intercrop of onions and peppers produced a lower total and marketable yield of onions than onions grown as a monocrop.

Table 8. Effect of intercropping and varieties on yield and yield component parameters of onion

Onion varieties	Intercropping vegetable's	BL	BD	BOY	WTB	TBY	UNMB Y	MBY
Adama red	Carrot	3.55 ^{bcd}	3.74 ^{de}	70.14 ^d	64.24 ^c	32.12 ^c	0.68 ^f	31.44 ^c
	Tomato	3.44 ^{cde}	4.16 ^{cd}	69.93 ^d	63.15 ^c	31.58 ^{cd}	0.71 ^{d^{ef}}	30.86 ^{cd}
	Lettuce	3.75 ^{bcd}	3.83 ^{cde}	70.57 ^d	60.19 ^{cde}	30.10 ^{cde}	0.73 ^{de}	29.37 ^{cde}
Bombay red	Adama red	2.83 ^f	3.22 ^e	64.28 ^d	51.74 ^g	25.87 ^g	1.31 ^a	24.57 ^g
	Carrot	4.13 ^b	4.26 ^{cd}	85.67 ^c	58.34 ^{def}	29.17 ^{ef}	0.50 ^g	28.67 ^{de}
	Tomato	3.95 ^{bc}	3.90 ^{cd}	83.56 ^c	57.60 ^{ef}	28.80 ^{ef}	0.69 ^{ef}	28.11 ^{ef}
	Lettuce	3.27 ^{def}	3.81 ^{cde}	80.48 ^c	57.02 ^{ef}	28.51 ^{ef}	0.75 ^d	27.77 ^{ef}
Nafis	Bombay red	2.98 ^{ef}	3.77 ^{cde}	67.46 ^d	54.57 ^{fg}	27.29 ^{fg}	1.22 ^b	26.07 ^{fg}
	Carrot	5.42 ^a	5.30 ^a	110.40 ^a	80.35 ^a	40.43 ^a	0.30 ⁱ	40.13 ^a
	Tomato	4.13 ^b	5.05 ^a	103.09 ^b	73.07 ^b	36.54 ^b	0.39 ^h	36.14 ^b
	Lettuce	4.10 ^b	5.04 ^{ab}	100.80 ^b	70.96 ^b	35.48 ^b	0.53 ^g	34.95 ^b
	Nafis	3.47 ^{cde}	4.40 ^{bc}	83.34 ^c	62.57 ^{cd}	29.61 ^{de}	0.94 ^c	28.67 ^{de}
Mean		3.75	4.21	82.48	62.82	31.29	0.73	30.56
LSD		0.59	0.64	6.35	4.41	2.30	0.05	2.31
Significant level		*	Ns	**	**	**	***	**
CV		9.44	9.01	4.56	4.15	4.35	4.16	4.46

BL=bulb length, BD =bulb diameter, BOY=bulb biomass yield, WTB= weight of yield, TBW=total bulb weight, UNBY=Unmarketable bulb yield, MBY= marketable bulb yield,

*, ** and ***= significant at $P \leq 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001 probability levels; Ns=not significant at 5% probability levels

Economic Analysis

In the current study, the highest gross income per unit of area was recorded in onion intercropping compared to sole cropping treated with onion and untreated (Table 9). A greater gross income of 708768 ETB (the Ethiopian currency) ha⁻¹ was obtained by intercropping Nafis with carrots, whereas 628694 ETB ha⁻¹ was obtained from intercropping Nafis with tomatoes. This may be because different species on the same plot fetch different prices when harvest time arrives. On the other hand, treated (Adama red) 267,446 ETBha⁻¹ produced the

lowest gross return per hectare (Table 9). Compared to growing onions only, intercropping vegetables with onions adds value, diversifies output, and reduces production costs.

Consistent with current results, Hossain et al. [30] observed that intercropping onions with tomatoes or carrots yielded a superior economic return when it came to managing onion thrips. According to Aswathanarayanareddy et al. [38], beans, maize, bhendi, onion, garlic, brinjal and chilli intercropped with other plants were much better than those with a lower infestation of whiteflies, thrips, aphids, jassids, and pod borers and produced a greater yield than a solo crop.

The highest marginal return was recorded from the intercropping of Nafis with carrot, with a value of 80827%, followed by the intercropping of Nafis with tomato, with a value of 9323% (Table 9). Consequently, the combination of treatment of intercropping Nafis with carrots and Bombay red with tomato yielded the highest net benefit (642,310.3 ETB/ha). Endriyas et al. [39] support this study by demonstrating that the Nafis variety outperforms the other two varieties that were tested in terms of yield. Similar findings were demonstrated by Abaynew et al. [40] and Yechale et al. [41], highlighting the significance of partial budget analysis in economic research.

Table 9. Effect of intercropping and varieties on economic analysis of onion

Onivar	Inter	MBY	ADMY	GI	TVC	NB	MRR%	DA
AR	NI	24.56	36845	267446	5440	225161	-	ND
AR	CR	31.44	47160	494921	6095	441666		DA
AR	TT	30.86	46290	511763	8067	457406	8841	D
AR	L	29.36	44045	448224	5645	398534		D
BR	NI	26.07	39100	270731	5615	226016	-	ND
BR	CR	28.67	43005	503758	6115	454638		D
BR	TT	28.11	42163	515963	8185	465615	9323	D
BR	L	27.77	41648	427076	5733	379695		D
NS	NI	28.67	43005	303138	5790	254343	-	ND
NS	CR	40.13	60188	708768	6270	642310	80827	D
NS	TT	36.14	54215	628694	8272	566207		D
NS	L	34.95	52418	507405	5820	449168		D

Onivar = Onion varieties, Inter = Intercropping, NI = none intercropping, CR = Carrot, TT = Tomato, L= Lettuce, BR= Bombay red, NS= Nafis, AR= Adama red, MBY= marketable bulb yield, ADMY=adjacent marketable bulb yield, GI=Gross income, TVC= total variable cost, NB=net benefits, MRR=marginal rate of return, DA=dominance analysis, D=dominant, ND=non dominant.

Correlation analysis

The correlation coefficients between each pair of characters studied are presented in Table 10. Thus, it was observed that marketable bulb yield was highly significantly ($P < 0.01$) and negatively correlated with day 15 ($r = -0.86^{***}$), day 30 ($r = -0.75^{***}$), day 45 ($r = -0.49^{**}$), day 60 ($r = -0.40^*$), day 75 ($r = -0.53^{**}$), day 90 ($r = -0.49^{**}$), and day 105 ($r = -0.53^{**}$). This shows that the use of different intercropping and solo varieties of onion for onion thrips indicates a decrease in marketable onion yield. The commercial bulb yield was very significantly ($p < 0.001$) and positively correlated with the number of leaves ($r = 0.65^{***}$), the height of the plant ($r = 0.78^{***}$), the diameter of the bulb length ($r = 0.78^{***}$), the diameter of the bulb ($r = 0.81^{***}$), biomass bulb yield ($r = 0.79^{***}$), the weight of the bulb ($r = 0.98^{***}$) and the total bulb yield ($r = 0.99^{***}$). This shows that the use of different combinations of vegetable intercropping and onion varieties to increase vegetative growth results in indirect selection of vegetable intercropping and onion variety combinations for increasing onion yield. However, marketable bulb yield was very highly significant and negatively correlated to

unmarketable bulb yield ($r = -0.81^{***}$). Also, unmarketable bulb yield was very highly significantly ($p < 0.001$) and negatively correlated to number of leaves ($r = -0.70^{***}$), plant height ($r = -0.80^{***}$), leaf length ($r = -0.70^{***}$), bulb length ($r = -0.79^{***}$), bulb diameter ($r = -0.70^{***}$), biomass of bulb yield ($r = -0.77^{***}$), weight of bulb ($r = -0.77^{***}$), total bulb yield ($r = -0.79^{***}$) and marketable yield ($r = -0.81^{***}$). This shows that the use of different intercropping and solo varieties of onion increases the number of onion thrips or causes severe damage to the crop. Negative mutualism for onion yield indicates a decrease in marketable onion yield.

Similarly, the average bulb weight was positively correlated and very significant ($P < 0.001$) with the number of leaves ($r = 0.63^{***}$), plant height ($r = 0.77^{***}$), leaf length ($r = 0.76^{***}$), bulb length ($r = 0.76^{***}$), bulb diameter ($r = 0.80^{***}$), and biomass bulb yield ($r = 0.78^{***}$). This research indicates that the number of leaves, plant height, leaf length, bulb length, bulb diameter, and biomass bulb yield parameters are positively correlated with the yield per plant bulb weight. These findings are also in agreement with the results of Cheema et al. [42], who reported that bulb weight was positively correlated with bulb diameter. It was also observed that plant height was very highly significantly ($P < 0.001$) and positively correlated with number of leaves ($r = 0.86^{***}$), leaf length ($r = 0.93^{***}$), bulb length ($r = 0.73^{***}$), bulb diameter ($r = 0.79^{***}$), biomass bulb yield ($r = 0.94^{***}$), weight of bulb ($r = 0.77^{***}$), total bulb yield ($r = 0.76^{***}$), and marketable yield ($r = 0.78^{***}$). The result indicated that a change in one of these parameters by vegetable intercropping and varieties can lead to a positive change in plant height. Similarly, the number of leaves was very significantly ($P < 0.001$) and positively correlated with the height of the plant ($r = 0.86^{***}$), leaf length ($r = 0.87^{***}$), the length of the bulb ($r = 0.76^{***}$), bulb diameter ($r = 0.72^{***}$), the biomass bulb yield ($r = 0.83^{***}$), bulb weight of the bulb ($r = 0.63^{***}$), the total yield of the bulb ($r = 0.64^{***}$), and marketable yield ($r = 0.65^{***}$). This association indicates that an increased photosynthetic area in response to vegetable intercropping and onion varieties has noticeably contributed to enhanced onion yield and quality, which could be through the production of more assimilates and finally translocate to the bulb yield.

Table 10. Simple Pearson's correlation coefficient Analysis for number of onion thrips per plant, growth and yield component parameters

Parameters	Day 15	Day 30	Day 45	Day 60	Day 75	Day 90	Day 105	NL	PH	LL
Day 15	1									
Day 30	0.89***	1								
Day 45	0.63***	0.78***	1							
Day 60	0.51**	0.67***	0.78***	1						
Day 75	0.60***	0.71***	0.73***	0.95***	1					
Day 90	0.53**	0.65***	0.66***	0.91***	0.95***	1				
Day 105	0.63***	0.73***	0.72***	0.91***	0.95***	0.97***	1			
NL	-0.61***	-0.69***	-0.70***	-0.80***	-0.87***	-0.85***	-0.86***	1		
PH	-0.71***	-0.72***	-0.62***	-0.74***	-0.86***	-0.81***	-0.81***	0.86***	1	
LL	-0.73***	-0.67***	-0.58**	-0.76***	-0.86***	-0.86***	-0.83***	0.87***	0.93***	1
BL	-0.73***	-0.82***	-0.57**	-0.55**	-0.64***	-0.59**	-0.63**	0.76***	0.73***	0.70***
BD	-0.70***	-0.66***	-0.41*	-0.49**	-0.64***	-0.65***	-0.68***	0.72***	0.79***	0.78***
BOY	-0.73***	-0.76***	-0.56**	-0.70***	-0.83***	-0.79***	-0.80***	0.83***	0.94***	0.93***
WTB	-0.83***	-0.70***	-0.44**	-0.37*	-0.50**	-0.49**	-0.52**	0.63***	0.77***	0.76***
TBY	-0.84***	-0.73***	-0.46**	-0.38*	0.51**	-0.48**	-0.51**	0.64***	0.76***	0.76***
UNMBY	0.90***	0.91***	0.78***	0.62***	0.70***	0.59**	0.69***	-0.70***	-0.80***	-0.70***
MBY	-0.86***	-0.75***	-0.49**	-0.40*	-0.53**	-0.49**	-0.53**	0.65***	0.78***	0.76***

NL=number of leaf, PH=plant height, LL=leaf length, BL= bulb length, BD= bulb diameter, BOY= bulb biomass yield, WTB= weight of yield, TBW=total bulb weight, UNBY=Unmarketable bulb yield, MBY= marketable bulb yield, *, ** and ***= significant at $P \leq 0.05, 0.01$ and 0.001 probability levels respectively, Ns= not significant at 5% probability levels.

CONCLUSIONS

It is necessary to quantify the impact of onion thrips on yield and yield-related characteristics of onion varieties and to ascertain how well onion varieties integrate with vegetable intercropping to reduce onion thrips and boost production. During the irrigated cropping season in the research area, marketable bulb production was significantly reduced due to onion thrips. When three methods of vegetable intercropping are applied, the effects of the varieties of onions and the intercropping techniques interact with onion thrips. Variety and vegetable intercropping were shown to be significantly different in onion production and most yield-related characteristics; intercropping on Nafis, in particular, produced high and comparable yields. However, the percentage of thrips, the number of thrips reduction percentage, the infestation, the growth parameter, the reduction of the leaf damage severity scale, and the yield components of the onion crop were all significantly impacted by the interaction of onion varieties with onion vegetable intercropping.

Onion types interplanted with vegetables greatly decreased the number of onion thrips and the extent of their harm. This demonstrates that the population of onion thrips on the onion crop is reduced by Nafis with carrot and Bombay red with carrot. When Nafis and carrots were interplanted, the least amount of leaf damage was seen. On intercropped Nafis with carrots, the maximum marketable bulb yield of onion was observed, followed by Nafis with tomato. When it came to onion varieties, Nafis was the most productive, followed by Bombay red. The best-performing intercropping strategy in this study, it may be stated, was Nafis with carrots. In order to preserve onion yield, intercropping is therefore appropriate in this situation, particularly for small-scale growers. Additionally, this method would be perfect for integrated pest management in the production of organic vegetables. An intercropping system's benefits included decreased insect pests, increased productivity per unit of land, and promoted the number of beneficial insects. It lowered financial risk in the case of crop failure and permitted crop diversification.

According to this study, intercropping vegetables alongside different varieties of onions decreases onion thrips and increases onion yield. Thus, reducing the quantity of onion thrips per plant and the degree of damage was achieved by intercropping carrot with Nafis. Carrot and Nafis intercropping produced the highest yield and marginal rate of return. Therefore, farmers in the research area and other regions with comparable agro-ecological characteristics can benefit from it. To produce more trustworthy data, more research on the diversity of intercropping vegetables, locations, planting seasons, and onion varieties should be taken into consideration.

Conflict of interest- The authors declare that there is no competing of interests.

Data Availability Statement-The data used to support the findings of this study are included within the article.

Authors' Declaration- The authors hereby affirm that the material given in this article is their own, and agree to take responsibility for any claims made regarding its content. It has not been simultaneously submitted to another journal or been published in another publication.

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